

**BOLALAR KITOBXONLIGI VA MEDIYA MUHITIDA BOLALIK
KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI.****Eraliyeva Zamira Rasuljonovna**

Teacher of Kokand University

Annotatsiya: Maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalik konsepti haqida tushuncha. Bolalik konseptining ifodalanishi va badiiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishda bolalar kitobxonligini takomillashtirish yuzasidan ilmiy qarashlar, tarbiyachi pedagoglar uchun tavsiyalar, metodlardan na'munalar va natijalari bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Konsept, mediya, mental, etnik, assotsiativ, emotsional, kognitiv-semantik, lingvokulturologik, verbal.

Аннотация: В статье дается понимание понятия детства в дошкольном возрасте. Описаны научные взгляды на совершенствование детского чтения в развитии представлений о детстве и развитии художественного мышления, рекомендации для педагогов, образцы и результаты методик.

Ключевые слова: Концепт, медиа, ментальный, этнический, ассоциативный, эмоциональный, когнитивно-семантический, лингвокультурный, вербальный.

**CHILDREN'S READING AND EXPRESSION OF CHILDHOOD
CONCEPT IN THE MEDIA.**

Annotation: The article gives an understanding of the concept of childhood in preschool age. Scientific views on the improvement of children's reading in the development of ideas about childhood and the development of artistic thinking, recommendations for teachers, examples and results of methods are described.

Key words: Concept, media, mental, ethnic, associative, emotional, cognitive-semantic, linguocultural, verbal.

Child education, which has had an important role as an indispensable value for centuries, has not lost its importance. A. Oripov, a well known Uzbek poet, mentioned: "I don't know what kind of person Alisher's mother was," and H. Olimjon's lines "I heard many tales, my grandmother would tell me" indicate that Uzbek women have been intelligent and enlightened since ancient times. Therefore, in the linguistic landscape of the Uzbek people, the concepts of family, family and child are harmoniously interrelated. Here, it is worth noting that the concept is a unit that actively moves in the perception of the world, which is mentally formed in his mind, reflects the worldview of the speakers of the language, national and ethnic characteristics. A concept is an idea about objects and events, which reflects their general and significant signs, and a concept is a set of opinions that have gained some generality in some way, so it is not only abstract, but concrete-associative. and includes emotional-evaluative traits.

In modern linguistics, the term "concept" refers to knowledge about the world

Which is used as one of the forms of demonstration. The term "concept" was first brought into science by philosophers such as W. Hobbes, P. Abeloire, and W. Ockham during the period of medieval conceptualism. To this day, there are different opinions, definitions and approaches to studying the concept. In recent times, important information about the concept has started to appear in Uzbek linguistics. In this matter Sh. Safarov, A. Nurmanov, O'. Uusupov, A. Abuduazizov, A. Opinions in the works of such scientists as Mamatov, D. Ashurova, M. Dzhusupov, M. Galieva, D. Agzamova, D. Khudauberganova, N. Tokhtakhojaeva, B. Mengliev, and Z. Kholmonova mentioned its specific characteristics. Sh. In Safarov's opinion, the concept is a unit of thought, which is based on a generalization of concept, image and linguistic meaning. It is also recognized by linguists that the concept is a multi-layered and multifaceted mental structure. Because it simultaneously demonstrates psychological, cognitive-semantic and linguocultural aspects, it is considered an object of cognitive and linguocultural research. When studying internal verbalizers of the concept, special attention should be paid to the internal form as the main motivation of

the word. About this, Potebnua emphasized that "the word, in fact, does not express the whole idea taken for its content, but only one of its features."

It is the word which expresses a concept in the analysis of this concept (verbalizer). According to the internal form of etymology and its defined concept content it is necessary to determine the connection. When we think about the central and peripheral vocabulary units of the concept of "Childhood", we can see that the combination "Healthy child" is prominent in social, scientific, artistic and religious discourse. The complex tasks aimed at the development of a healthy child in the State programs of a number of schools serve to fully reveal the content of the development of the child's physical and mental capabilities under this combination. We would not be wrong if we say that the slogan "Healthy child" is an effort to make the future generation, the growing generation, mentally, spiritually and physically healthy and grow up healthy. The motto "Healthy child" should be one of the main concerns of every nation, and people. Because the future generation is the generation that determines the future of every nation, state, people. They are the seeds of hope for this state and nation. "In working with children in preschool education, language plays an important role. Children like to listen to folk tales, poems, stories. Children's literature, first of all, gives joy to children with its interesting content, the beauty of artistic images, the expressiveness of the language, the musicality of poetic words. At the same time, it has an educational effect on children. The value of good literature is that it affects the child's growth in every aspect. Art literature protects the children's work and life of the nature of the country, their deeds and heroism, stories from children's lives, children's games, pastimes and work. Understanding the inner world of people, their characters, emotions, behavior, as well as works of art and literature, make the child to be excited, feel sorry for the heroes of the work, or condemn them. The best works of art and literature give children their own sense of what is good-good, fair-unfair, right-wrong.

The teacher should familiarize the children with many works of children's literature in each group. The teacher develops the ability to perceive literary works in

children. A child should not only listen to the work and learn its content, but also feel the feelings and emotions described by the author. Some elements of analysis of the content and forms of the work are included in preschool educational organizations. At the time of transition to school, every child should be able to identify the main characters told in the work, to know his attitude towards them (who liked him and why), to be able to determine the form of the work (poem, story, fairy tale). It is necessary to train children to listen together, to answer questions carefully and to ask questions based on the read work, to look carefully at the illustrations, and to have a good attitude towards the book. Kindergarten children should develop the ability to be devoted to books, to be interested in learning, and to share their impressions of the works they have listened to.

Most of the works presented in the State Program of Preschool Education - First Step constitute the golden fund of children's literature. In this, the educator should follow the published books, read critical articles in magazines and participate in the discussion of children's books. The teacher should familiarize the children with many works of children's literature in each group. An important task of the kindergarten is to ensure that children master the content of the works and understand them correctly. Children should be able to memorize a part of the works, and copy the part more closely to the text.

When you compare a child who attended kindergarten with a child who did not attend kindergarten, it is not unusual to notice a huge difference in their thinking level. That's why we raised the issue of pre-school education system to the level of state policy and started great work in this regard. If we do not carry out this work thoroughly, it will be difficult to achieve a quality change in the entire education system, to ensure the continuity of education, said Shavkat Mirziouev.

Based on these thoughts, a person who cares for the future of children, who can educate a free, creative, well-rounded person is definitely an educator.

In today's world, the demand for such a competent teacher is increasing. Competence (eng. "competency" - "ability") means effective use of theoretical

knowledge in any activity, possession of high-level professional skills and competence, skill and talent. Competence is the possession of knowledge, skills, qualifications and experience necessary for any person to work effectively in the field of his activity, nowadays these qualities are personal qualities (high civility, broad outlook, high It is a concept that is related to intelligence, independent thinking, etc.).

The use of modern technology : Educators should use modern technology, taking into account the low level of familiarity with books for children today. They can present the stories, poems, or parables they want to share in video or audio form. In this case, it will be more clear that the electronic presentation of the story, which is intended to be introduced in the literature, will achieve the formation of a more accurate image in education.

Making a reading corner : Giving children a corner that does not distract them and is free from external noise will increase their interest in the book and giving them information in this room will give them a sense of fluency and the formation can be achieved. Even small tents can serve as "yucha" for children. However, if this angle forms in the natural order, it will also give an effective result.

Taking children to nature tours often: It allows educators to develop their knowledge about nature in a wider and practical way through tours (excursions). Accompanying the literature that they recited in Saur Jarauon, reading excerpts from them or making oral stories also gives its positive effect. Tales and stories about the seasons, their characteristics, natural plants, and animals are very useful in Saur jarauoni.

"Computer didactic method".

Preschool education organization No. 5 "Kaldirgoch" belonging to the Preschool Education Department of Toragorgon District of Namanagan Province used this approach in the small group (A) of 17 children.

Computer didactic games can be implemented in the educational process in preschool educational organizations, including elementary mathematical concepts, familiarization with numbers with children and together with them we create numbers

with flower petals, numbers, their color, shape and size to encourage the study of similar objects. Computer didactic games have their own pedagogical and psychological aspects, which are currently not fully explored. I will give you some information about them.

Preschool educational organizations can also use computer-based educational and developmental games based on multimedia technologies. At this point, it should be noted that computer training and development games are conducted in compliance with all the laws and rules of didactics. Forms of conducting games consist of training, training and recreational games. Multimedia educational and developmental games are part of didactic games and are aimed at implementing the educational process in preschool education organizations.

In the "Swallow" group, we used this method to implement computer didactic games in the educational process, including introducing elementary mathematical ideas to children with numbers and together with them we create numbers with flower petals, numbers, their color, they help to study the shape and similar objects. Computer didactic games have their own pedagogical and psychological aspects, which are currently not fully explored. I will give you some information about them. In this case, children's fever has increased and we have achieved an effective result.

We present the results of the research conducted in the development centers active in preschool educational organizations on the improvement of children's speech.

We focused mainly on the formation of children's speech competences, that is, children's ability to learn new words, to be able to speak by looking at pictures, to answer questions, to listen and understand, to use words such as nouns, adjectives, numbers, and verbs in their speech. We focused on their support.

Analysis of questions and answers

T/r	Questions	Yes	Nope	Someti mes
1	Does the development of children's speech take place at the expense of words?	55 (91%)	0(0%)	5 (8%)
2	Do parents need help in improving speech?	30 (50%)	11 (18%)	19 (31%)
3	Are there visual aids that encourage speech development?	25 (42%)	30 (50%)	5 (8%)
4	Does the teacher need to be creative in teaching language skills?	42 (70%)	8(13%)	10 (16%)
5	Are you interested in methods that activate children in the classes?	52 (86%)	5 (8%)	3 (5%)

All 60 of the respondents who took part in the questionnaire were teachers of preschool educational institutions, and they answered the questions voluntarily. 55 - 91% of the respondents answered "yes", 0 answered "no", and 5 - 8% answered "sometimes" to the question of whether children's speech can be developed at the expense of words .

30 - 50% of the respondents answered "yes", 11 - 18% answered "no", 19 - 31% answered "sometimes" to the question of whether parents are involved in improving speech .

Are there visual aids that encourage speech development? 25 - 42% of the participants answered "yes", 30 - 50% answered "no", 8 - 8% answered "sometimes", of respondents answered "yes", 8 - 13% answered "no", and 10 - 16% answered "sometimes" to the question, "Does the teacher need to be creative in teaching language skills? " they gave

Are you interested in methods that activate children in the classes? 52 - 86% of the respondents answered "yes", 5 - 8% answered "no", and 3 - 5% answered "sometimes" and gave their examples of oral creativity to children. they gave information about the success and shortcomings of the activity in teaching.

It can be seen from the analysis that there are educators who need to work on themselves as well as educators who organize training sessions on an interactive level.

In conclusion, the effectiveness of training in development centers for improving children's speech should be increased. Because through effective training, the child keeps the learned knowledge fast and firmly in his memory. Also, through these activities, every day, every hour of the children will be interesting and enjoyable. After all, developing the abilities of children in pre-school educational organizations and educating them to be mature and perfect in all aspects is one of the primary tasks of educators and pedagogues.

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